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MUNDARIJA

PEDAGOGIKA

Yulbarsova X.A. Bo'lajak sotsiologlarda ijtimoiy kompetentlikni rivojlantirish tuzilmasi va tavsifi	4
Xushnazarova M.N. Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarni ijtimoiy pedagogik amaliyotga tayyorlashda pedagogika fanining samarali usullaridan foydalanish	10
Raxmedova M.A. Mahmud az-Zamaxshariyning ma'naviy merosidan yoshlarni axloqiy tarbiyalashda foydalanish imkoniyatlari	13
Ismoilov Y.Q. Bo'lajak jismoniy madaniyat o'qituvchilarini ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiyalashning texnologik masalalari	17
Iminova H.M. Ta'lim tizimiga konsentrlangan ta'limni integratsiya qilishning zamonaviy pedagogik tendensiyalari	20
Muladjanova G.A., Mullajonova M.D. Oliy ta'lim talabalarining sun'iy intellekt tizimlaridan foydalanish kompetentligini takomillashtirish	25
Wang Ping. Exploration of ethnic music elements in chinese piano works	29
Kadirov A.M., Ergasheva Sh.Q. The role of fine arts in installing the values of human dignity in general education pupils	32
Nadirxanova N.A. Enhancing creative competence in students through the steam educational methodology: integrating visual arts and engineering graphics	38
Axmedova D.X. Interfaol usulda rag'batlantirishning o'quvchilar ta'lim-tarbiyasiga ijobiy ta'siri	44
O'rinboyev M. I. Fizika o'qitish amaliyotida metakognitiv faoliyatlarni takomillashtirish	48
Burxonova M.M., Sirojiddinov B.A. Amaliy mashq va masalalarning kontekstual asoslari hamda umumta'lim maktablarda qo'llanilishi bo'yicha pedagogik-metodik aspektlar	51
To'raxonova B.T. Bo'lajak pedagog-psixologlarni tarbiyaviy faoliyatini tashkil etishga tayyorlashning pedagogik imkoniyatlari	54
O'smanova D.Z. Zamonaviy dars jarayonida adabiy-nutqiy kompetensiyani shakllantirish, ilg'or pedagogik texnologiyalar orqali rivojlantirish	57
Xudoyberganova M.A. Talabalarga adabiyotni o'qitishda ijtimoiy tarmoqlardan foydalanishning samarali texnologiyalari	61
Iminova D.N. Innovativ loyihalar vositasida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida o'qish motivatsiyasini rivojlantirishning mazmuni	65
Abdulmadjidova M.D. Ilk o'spirinlik davrida mehnatga munosabatning shakllanishi	68
Dushabayeva G.M. Mustaqil ta'limda chizmachilik fanidan kompyuter dasturlarda foydalanishning ahamiyati	71
Utanova V.M. Diskurs tahlili: umumiy ta'rif, metodologiya va misol	75
Qoraboyev J.B., Qoraboyeva N.N. Ingliz va o'zbek tillarida frazeologik ma'no tuzilishi	78
Umarov A.V. Ilmiy-ma'rifiy media loyihalar – talabalarining mediasavodxonligi va axborot madaniyatini rivojlantiruvchi didaktik vosita sifatida	81
Qodirova O.S. Maktabgacha ta'lim yoshida bolalarning ta'lim faoliyatiga faol tashabbuskorlik munosabatini shakllantirishning ijtimoiy-psixologik xususiyatlari	86
Aslonov X.Sh. Dasturlangan laboratoriya ishlarida yarimo'tkazgichlarning ta'qiqlangan zona kengligi tushunchasi	89
Bakirov I.H. Boks sport turida musobaqalarning o'tkazish turlari va musobaqa faoliyati	94
Saidg'aniyev S.O. Bolalar uchun sport gimnastikasi	98
Tojiboyeva N.T. Ta'lim muhitida o'zini-o'zi boshqarishda qiyin bo'lgan o'smirlarning hissiy qulayligining psixologik jihatlari	100
Dushabayev D.Sh. Umum ta'lim maktablarda jismoniy tarbiya darslarida zamonaviy ta'lim texnologiyalaridan foydalanish	103
Abdullaev G'A. The method of determination of aerobic and anaerobic treshhold by heart rate of athletes in the development of endurance qualities in athletics training (In the case of middle and long distance runners)	106
Qurbonova F.M. Talabalarining jamoada ishlash qobiliyatlarini kollobratsiya asosida shakllantirishning psixologik xususiyatlari	110
Shobduraximova U.T. Tavakallchilikka asoslangan virtual o'yinlar va ularning jamiyatga salbiy ta'siri	113
Hasanova S.K. Development of creative thinking of primary class students based on pirls' flows	115
No'monova A.N. O'zbekiston ta'lim tizimiga tasviriy san'atning rang tasvir yo'nalishini tadqiq etishning dolzarb masalalari	119
Toshtemirov Q.Q. Umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablari musiqa madaniyati darslarida milliy musiqa merosi "shashmaqom"ni o'rganishning ahamiyati	122
Gofurjanova N.K. Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarini xalqaro baholash dasturlaridagi ishtirokining ta'lim sifatini oshirishdagi o'rni	126
IJTIMOIY GUMANITAR FANLAR	
Yusupova S.N., Bakhronov B. Ijtimoiy-gumanitar fanlarning dolzarb muamolari	129
Olimova Z.I. Abdulla Avloniyning Turkiston o'lkasidagi jadidchilik harakatiga qo'shgan hissasi	132
Mirzayeva B. Maishiy zo'ravonlikning ijtimoiy-falsafiy mohiyati	134

mumkin, masalan, idrokni yaxshilash va stressdan xalos bo'lish. O'yinchilar o'zlarining o'yin odatlarini yodda tutishlari va virtual o'yinlarga mas'uliyatli va muvozanatli yondashishlari muhimdir. Virtual o'yinlarning ommabopligi o'sishda davom etar ekan, ularning jamiyatga ta'sirini yaxshiroq tushunish va potentsial salbiy ta'sirlarni yumshatish uchun strategiyalarni ishlab chiqish uchun qo'shimcha tadqiqotlar talab etiladi.

2012-yilga kelib, bunday totalizatorlar soni sezilarli oshdi. Shuningdek, ayrim onlayn kazino kompaniyalari yopilib, hatto jinoiy javobgarlikka tortildi. Sababi, ularning maqsadi firibgarlik yo'li bilan pul to'plash edi. 2016 yildan boshlab "1 xbet", "mostbet", "lenabet" kabi onlayn betting ilovalari dunyo bo'ylab keng yoyildi

Xulosa qilib shuni aytish mumkinki, bunday o'yinlar insonda qaramlikni vujudga keltirib, katta miqdordagi pul mablag'lari sarflashiga va ayrim fuqarolarning o'z joniga qasd qilish, firibgarlik, byudjet mablag'larni talon-toraj qilish kabi harkatlar sodir etilishiga sabab bo'lmoqda.

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DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE THINKING OF PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS BASED ON PIRLS' FLOWS

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Abstract. *This article describes the pedagogical and psychological aspects of the development of creative thinking of elementary school students based on PIRLS tasks.*

Key words: *creativity, International Assessment Program, PIRLS tasks, elementary school, student, ability, talent, personality.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье описаны педагогические и психологические аспекты развития творческого мышления учащихся младших классов на основе заданий PIRLS.*

Ключевые слова: *креативность, Международная программа оценки, задания PIRLS, начальная школа, ученик, способности, талант, личность.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada PIRLS topshiriqlari asosida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida ijodiy fikrlashni rivojlantirishning pedagogik va psixologik jihatlari yoritilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *ijodkorlik, Xalqaro baholash dasturi, PIRLS, boshlang'ich sinf, o'quvchi, qobiliyat, iste'dod, shaxsiyat*

The use of pedagogical evaluation technologies developed by the world's leading experts allows to create a national system of evaluating the quality of education in Uzbekistan at the level of world standards.

Below we will consider the methods of applying the PIRLS international program, which evaluates reading literacy in primary grades, to reading literacy classes.

The PIRLS international project (Progress in International Reading Literacy Study) allows to compare the quality of reading and comprehension of primary 4th graders in different countries. Research is conducted every five years.

As part of the study, the reading quality of students who are completing the 4th grade will be tested, because this fourth year is an important stage in the development of children - by this time, students should acquire reading literacy at such a level that this skill can be used in education. It is necessary to become the main tool for the next stage of acquisition [1].

Reading literacy is the foundation of academic success, and the PIRLS is a valuable tool for examining the extent to which new or revised strategies affect acquisition. The PIRLS assessment program is based on a comprehensive framework that includes the main learning objectives of art reading experience, acquiring and using information, and searching for information on the Internet.

Today, many conditions are created for students to develop their abilities, independently choose a profession, and acquire modern professions. Also, by 2030, Uzbekistan will be among the first 30 advanced countries in the world according to PISA (The Program for International Student Assessment), PIRLS (Progress in International Reading and Literacy Study) rating of the international student assessment program. intended to be achieved. PIRLS (Progress in International Reading Literacy Study) is an international assessment system that assesses the quality of reading and comprehension levels of primary school students in different countries.

In the decision No. 997 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 8, 2018 "On measures to organize international studies in the field of education quality assessment in the public education system" (assessment), TIMSS (assessing the level of mastery of 4th and 8th grade students in mathematics and natural sciences), PISA (assessing the literacy level of 15-year-old students in reading, mathematics and natural sciences), TALIS (in general secondary educational institutions of managerial and pedagogic personnel organization of international research on international evaluation programs, such as studying the teaching and learning environment and working conditions of teachers).

PIRLS International Assessment Program is one of the programs that has its place in our educational system. When entering our educational system, students and teachers of Uzbekistan have been conducting a special preparation process [2].

Creativity (lat., ing. "create" - creation, "creative" - creator) means the ability of creativity, which describes the readiness of an individual to produce new ideas and is part of talent as an independent factor. A person's creativity is manifested in his thinking, communication, feelings, and certain types of activities. Creativity describes a person as a whole or his specific features, mental sharpness. Also, creativity is reflected as an important factor of talent. Analyzing the above points of view on the issue of the components of creativity abilities, we can conclude that despite the difference in approaches to their definition, researchers unanimously define the quality of creative imagination and creative thinking as mandatory components of creativity abilities. Creativity ability is a factor of high creative development. and is expressed in various aspects of activity, including speech, writing and many other types.

As a result of the reforms implemented in our developing education system, huge economic growth indicators are being achieved, increasing the demand for qualified personnel and mature specialists in all fields. This in itself requires increasing the interest of our students in lessons and increasing the attention of teachers to all-round education. Developed countries consider the role of youth education in the development of society and human development to be important. That is why they pay special attention to the quality of education. At the same time, the concept of quality in the field of education became very popular in our country. Increasing the intellectual potential of the future young generation, forming a broad worldview is important not only for a specific country, but also for the international community.

The development of creativity in schoolchildren, first of all, a person-oriented approach, emotional-psychic mood, active, creative imagination, self-activation, independence, self-control, manifestation, expression, evaluation, requires the use of innovative educational technologies in the educational process. Abilities are a set of mental-individual characteristics that allow acquiring important knowledge, skills and abilities for productive activity.

The results of using PIRLS international assessment exercises in literacy classes show that primary 4th graders have a relatively low level of readiness to read texts and use these texts to improve their personal experience and knowledge [3].

During the analysis of the stage of completing the individual tasks of the international test, some difficulties faced by the students were revealed. In particular, the analysis of the results showed that the lack of a habit of referring to the text when any information needs to be clarified leads to two typical problems firstly, students do not distinguish well between the information presented in the text and the information they have based on their personal experience (about 37%), secondly, they are limited to vague assimilation of information in the text (about 26%).

It is very important to teach children to constantly refer to the text when answering questions, to pay attention to how the tasks are formulated, because the tasks are almost always "Relying on the text...", "Based on the text...", "What does the text say..." is given in the form .

If the question requires a detailed answer, students (up to 65%) have difficulties with the process of expressing thoughts in writing. We can witness that students who understand the read text well, in many cases, have difficulty in expressing their thoughts. They have difficulty formulating an answer to a question in the task, for example: "The little girl is an important character in this story. Explain why his place is so important in all the events that happened", "Why did the farmer's friend take the eagle to the mountains to make it fly? Give two reasons", "Explain why it is important to put soil and sand in alternating layers in a glass jar", "Explain why it is important to put potato and onion slices on top of the soil in the earthworm experiment" .

Currently, PIRLS defines reading literacy as the ability to understand and use forms of written language that are required and valued by society, as well as the ability to make meaning from texts in a variety of ways [4].

What if we pedagogues first of all prepare ourselves for PIRLS tasks... The purpose of this idea leads to the creation and formation of pedagogues who create national literature. For this, we need to allocate hours of independent study for primary education students and create a new PIRLS textbook for students.

In the process of independent education, students create stories based on the requirements of PIRLS, create evaluation criteria and, most importantly, understand what PIRLS is and its goals.

Activity is as necessary for abilities as water and air (activity creates conditions for its formation and development). Intellectual ability refers to the ability to use concepts and make logical generalizations. The following were determined as indicators of creativity: knowing the possibilities of setting a goal and realizing it, being able to explain one's goal; formulating cognitive tasks and putting forward hypotheses; to analyze one's learning activity; acquiring knowledge independently; are indicators of creativity. In the process of introducing the technology of the teaching module, the conditions for independent work of students were provided, they had the opportunity to analyze and control the process and results of their educational activities, internal and external aspects of education. guaranteed to achieve its goals. The theoretical analysis of the problem of development of creative abilities in the field of primary education includes the solution of two main issues [5].

The PIRLS international assessment program, which is recognized as a national program, is widely used in the educational system. First of all, we need to prepare our specialists for this process. After all, a pedagogue who knows the goals and tasks of PIRLS uses it purposefully. There is a lack of methodological manuals, methodological recommendations and literature in our educational system. However, we can create our national literature in the process of training specialists. Self-directed learning based on practical principles can help him. In the process of independent learning, students create stories based on research requirements. If the written stories can meet the requirements of the research, it can be published as a methodological guide. And I want to mention that we have enough theoretical information! We need methodical recommendations and manuals.

Firstly, to reflect the essence of developing creative abilities in the content of primary education; secondly, to use the scientific and pedagogical potential of primary education to develop the creative abilities of primary school students. At the current stage, we will try to describe the features of solving the above problems [6].

The concept of creative abilities is widely used in modern pedagogy. Modern psychology distinguishes various types of creative abilities: scientific, economic, intellectual, creative, professional, etc.

There are many exercises to develop creative thinking. One of the main goals of such intellectual games or exercises is to move away from usual and traditional ways of thinking and create new ideas, which can then be evaluated and the most useful can be selected. The first direction includes the organizational integrity of the process of developing creative abilities of the elementary school student.

Creative qualities of elementary school students can be formed only in the pedagogical process effectively organized at all levels of general education. This will be helped by the use of various organizational forms of teaching, tools, and effective methods of the pedagogical process. Starting with a new approach to education, we will start with the ability to study Define the following three directions of organization: organizational, meaningful and personal.

We should use foreign literature for initial preparation, our own national, educational stories and texts, and even fairy tales. If we can organize the questions and evaluation criteria correctly, new textbooks created on the basis of the 4k model can also help us. The integration of Pirls and new textbooks is a useful way to prepare for research and to acquire knowledge, skills and competencies of all disciplines. The "Little Walnut Tree" stylistic guide is also relevant for today.

This guide contains stories and tasks created on the basis of the PIRLS program, taking into account the development of students' critical and creative thinking, independent search for information, analytical processes and skills, the competencies of solving problem situations independently as a team. focused on issues of formation.

This includes the organizational structure of education, means, and pedagogical methods. The second direction reflects the meaningful integrity of the educational process in the conditions of primary education. Then, teaching technology (labor), like teaching all academic subjects, can reflect a holistic system in scientific, methodological, and practical relations. The third direction includes a holistic perception of the subject of education (teaching creativity) and considering it as a component of its social environment, in which it is at the same time creativity, work, as well as It functions as an object and a subject of the p-level educational environment [7].

The participation of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the PIRLS research serves to improve the quality of education, strengthen the country's reputation at the international level, and bring the students' knowledge to the level of international requirements.

Thus, in the process of developing creative abilities, we present the activity of the integrated process system of teaching creativity at the organizational, substantive and personal levels, which contributes to the objective view of the causal relationship between the theoretical, methodological and practical preparation of elementary school students. we determined the directions.

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O'ZBEKISTON TA'LIM TIZIMIGA TASVIRIY SAN'ATNING RANG TASVIR YO'NALISHINI TADQIQ ETISHNING DOLZARB MASALALARI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada O'zbekiston ta'lim tizimida san'at sohasiga bo'lgan ehtiyoj va san'at sohasiga berilayotgan e'tibor haqida so'z yuritilgan. Tasviriy san'atning rang tasvir yo'nalishi o'quvchilarning ijodiy qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish va estetik didini shakllantirishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Maqolada ranglarning ifoda kuchi, ularning kompozitsiyadagi o'rni va bir-biriga ta'siri bo'yicha ma'lumotlar va tavsiyalar berib o'tilgan.

